

D8.1 – Project Management Plan

30.03.2026

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Glossary and abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CH	Cultural Heritage
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hubs
DM	Dissemination Manager
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
EDP	European Data Portal
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GA	Grant Agreement
GAM	General Assembly Meeting
KET	Key Enabling Technologies
PM	Project Manager
PU	Public
QA	Quality Assurance
STL	Scientific / Technical Lead
TBD	To be determined
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Lead

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Executive Summary

This document provides all ARXIVE partners with a shared understanding of the project's working methods, procedures, and governance, ensuring that all contractual obligations with the European Commission are fulfilled. It offers a concise summary of the key project procedures, including governance structures, legal frameworks, project monitoring, reporting, financial management, and internal communication.

The handbook is designed to guide all beneficiaries in project management procedures, reduce administrative overhead, and increase operational efficiency. It serves as a frequently consulted reference tool, providing standardized templates, communication protocols, and contact information for quick and effective collaboration across the consortium. Official ARXIVE project documents are stored in the Collaborative Working Space, which serves as the central repository for document management and version control.

The handbook also defines internal communication guidelines, introduces collaborative workspaces and tools, specifies naming conventions and templates for document generation, and outlines the deliverable submission process to ensure high-quality outputs. Finally, it provides practical guidance on project reporting and administrative procedures, serving as a comprehensive reference for all consortium members. The handbook will be regularly updated throughout the project, and feedback from all partners is encouraged to maintain accuracy and relevance.

1 Introduction

This document complements existing ARXIVE project documents, including the Description of Action (DoA), Consortium Agreement (CA), and Grant Agreement (GA), avoiding unnecessary duplication while consolidating key operational procedures. The latest versions of these reference documents are stored in the project’s internal shared repository under the folder “Contractual Information.”

The handbook defines the structure and organization of the project, detailing the responsibilities and contact points of all partners. It also maps ARXIVE’s outputs and deliverables to the relevant grant agreement tasks and objectives, ensuring alignment with the project’s commitments. The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1:** Introduction
- **Chapter 2:** Contacts – details of the Coordinator and all partners
- **Chapter 3:** Project Structure Overview
- **Chapter 4:** Internal Communication
- **Chapter 5:** External Communication
- **Chapter 6:** Experiments Support & Research Methodology
- **Chapter 7:** Project Deliverables
- **Chapter 8:** Project Reporting
- **Chapter 9:** Innovation Management Process
- **Chapter 10:** Legal Framework
- **Chapter 11:** Financial Issues
- **Chapter 12:** Conclusions
- **Chapter 13:** References

1.1 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This handbook links ARXIVE’s grant agreement commitments to project outputs, mapping each deliverable and task to the respective management procedures and responsibilities. It describes the Project Management Plan (D8.1), which serves as the core handbook for the Project Coordination Office (PCO), project manager, and all partners. The plan sets out governance, project calendar, cluster and work-package responsibilities, reporting roles, communication mechanisms, and templates for formal documentation, ensuring consistent and high-quality project execution.

Table 1: Adherence to ARXIVE GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

Project Management		Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
T8.1 Project Management and administrative coordination	This task deals with all necessary project management tools and structures for the high quality, efficient and timely administrative coordination of the ARXIVE project. It incorporates the Administration management activities of the consortium, including procedures and	Section 2-11	Section 2: Contacts Section 3: Project Structure Overview Section 4: Internal Communication

	<p>guidelines for activity planning and monitoring, cost and time management, submission of periodic progress reports and cost Statements as well as preparation of annual review reports, review presentations, and timely submission of high-Quality deliverables to the European Commission (EC). LUH will be responsible for the day-to-day coordination of project-related activities and tasks, as well as the administrative management of the project. Contributions will be made by all the partners (participation in Project meetings, teleconferences, taking over responsibilities, reporting, coordination of allocated WPs and tasks). This Task will prepare and compile periodic financial reports, including Audit certificates. We will establish and maintain an internal tool to monitor resource expenditure (person months spending) per partner and per WP.</p>		<p>Section 5: External Communication</p> <p>Section 6: Experiments Support & Research</p> <p>Section 7: Project Deliverables</p> <p>Section 8: Project Reporting</p> <p>Section 9: Innovation Management Process</p> <p>Section 10: Legal Framework</p> <p>Section 11: Financial Issues</p>
<p>Project Management Plan Deliverable</p>			
<p><i>D8.1 Project Management Plan</i></p> <p>The project management plan - as core management handbook and structure - will provide guidelines for the Project Coordination Office (PCO) project manager (PM) and the Project members to follow during the full cycle of the project. The handbook will set out the governance, project calendar, cluster and work-package description and reporting roles and responsibilities for all partners. Moreover, it will define the communication mechanisms for the project's Partners and the templates for reporting and formal communication of the project's activities and outcomes.</p>			

2 Contacts

In this Chapter, the contacts of the Coordinator (LUH) as well as the other ARXIVE project partners are presented in detail.

2.1 Coordination

The administrative coordinator of the project is **GOTTFRIED WILHELM LEIBNIZ UNIVERSITAET, HANNOVER (LUH), WELFENGARTEN 1 – 30167 Hannover (Germany)**, www.uni-hannover.de. LUH also participates in the ARXIVE project by engaging its research center, L3S. The L3S Research Center was founded in 2001, as a joint research institute of several universities in Lower Saxony, officially associated with the LUH.

3 Project Structure Overview

The project structure is already described in the contractual information. However, the main boards and committees of the project are described in this section including the people involved, the responsibilities (figure 1 and table 4) and the frequency of meetings (figure 2) that can of course be changed if and when the project requires it. The ARXIVE Consortium consists of 9 partners. The management structure has the aim to be efficient and transparent in preparing and enforcing decisions at the Consortium level and in liaising with the European Commission.

The management has the following structure:

Figure 1: ARXIVE Management and Decision-Making Structure

3.1 Project Bodies

The following project bodies have an official function in the project management: The **Project Coordinator (PC)** acts as an intermediary between the consortium and the European Commission and is responsible for ensuring that the financial and contractual obligations defined in the **Grant Agreement (GA)** are met. The PC interacts with the European Commission and third parties about the project; provides strategic leadership for the project; coordinates and controls its major activities; and supervises the project progress against the planned schedule in budget and resources, identifies early technical and managerial problems, risk and trouble-shooting. The PC leads the Project Coordination Office that establishes and monitors quality Management

procedures for the review and signs off of project deliverables. The PC chairs the General Assembly Meeting (GAM) and the PMB.

The **General Assembly Meeting (GAM)** is established to review the overall progress of the project, acting as the common Forum for discussions and a body for high-level decisions. The General Assembly Meeting (GAM) consists of one delegate of each core beneficiary, meets at least twice a year, and is chaired by the Project Coordinator.

The **Project Management Board (PMB)** is the working committee of the General Assembly Meeting (GAM) to actively control the overall success of the project and to support the coordinator in the strategic management of the project, ensuring thereby that all beneficiaries can meet their individual responsibilities. The board consists of all **Work Package Leaders (WPL)** and PC. It meets at least twice a year and is chaired by the PC. Each Consortium Body shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its Members are present or represented (quorum). If the quorum is not reached, the chairperson of the Consortium Body shall convene another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more, the chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum of Members are present or represented.

Each Member of a Consortium Body present or represented in the meeting shall have one vote.

3.2 Supporting Groups and External Stakeholders

The following bodies support the implementation of the project and contribute to achieving its objectives. They do not, however, have a formal role in project management or decision-making.

Advisory Board (AB): The Advisory Board (AB) will provide independent strategic advice and high-level expert guidance to ARXIVE. It will support the overall development of the project and assess the effectiveness, transparency, and fairness of the Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) scheme, as well as the range of services and support provided to funded projects. The AB will contribute domain-specific expertise across relevant thematic areas and may issue recommendations to enhance project quality, impact, and strategic alignment. Its members may be consulted on selected Work Packages (WPs) and tasks in line with their expertise and availability. The Board will be established at project start (M1) and may be expanded during implementation to maintain appropriate expertise and representation. It is expected to consist of approximately 10 international experts covering all relevant target group areas. The AB will meet bi-annually and provide a brief report including recommendations for improvement. Additional meetings, including consultations with specific WPs, may be organised as necessary. Meetings will be chaired by the Project Coordinator (PC) and operationally overseen by the WP5 and WP6 leaders. The consortium has already secured the participation of distinguished experts, including Dr Laura Castro (Universidade Católica Portuguesa, CITAR), former Professor Yannis Kokkonas (Historical Bibliography), and Professor Giovanna Fossati (Utrecht University, Media Heritage, Technology and Culture).

ECCCH and ECHOES Liaison Task Force (ELTF): The ECCCH and ECHOES Liaison Task Force (ELTF) is composed of ARXIVE Work Package Leaders (WPLs) and serves as the primary bridge between ARXIVE and ECCCH-related initiatives and consortia. Its main responsibilities include:

- Facilitating communication, collaboration, and knowledge transfer with ECCCH, ensuring alignment with ECCCH objectives.
- Providing evidence-based recommendations and contributing to policy development processes.
- Monitoring and evaluating ARXIVE's effectiveness vis-à-vis ECHOES and using outcomes to inform future actions and policies.
- Supporting sustainable capacity-building by providing technical assistance, resources, and training to enhance the capabilities of cultural heritage stakeholders and secure the uptake of ARXIVE outcomes.

Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) Participants: The ARXIVE project integrates Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) as a strategic mechanism to engage external stakeholders, promote innovation, and facilitate the practical adoption and validation of tools, methods, and workflows developed within the project. FSTP ensures that ARXIVE's outputs are tested in real-world settings, fostering interoperability, knowledge sharing, and capacity building across the European cultural heritage ecosystem. FSTP participants play a central role in advancing the project's objectives by implementing experiments, cultural heritage preservation initiatives, and creative projects that directly contribute to ARXIVE's mission. These projects are designed to assess the effectiveness, usability, and impact of ARXIVE tools, while also contributing to the broader ECHOES and ECCCH framework. Through their work, participants help ensure that ARXIVE outputs are practical, user-centric, and aligned with the standards, interoperability requirements, and FAIR principles of ECCCH. FSTP activities are structured around two open calls:

- **Bibliography Beyond Boundaries:** This call supports up to 10 third parties in developing, refining, and enriching annotated bibliographies linked to cultural heritage organizations. Participants test innovative approaches for automated bibliographic annotation and collaborative workflows, leveraging AI-driven technologies to enhance interoperability and scalability within ECCCH.
- **Building Digital Narratives:** This call supports up to 10 third parties in creating digital storytelling solutions for documenting, analyzing, and communicating cultural heritage fieldwork, including archaeological excavations and related research. Projects focus on integrating ARXIVE tools into workflows to improve visualization, analysis, and accessibility of cultural heritage data, both within and beyond ECCCH.

Each selected third party receives a lump-sum grant of €20,000, with a total FSTP budget of €400,000. Funding is awarded competitively, ensuring transparency, inclusivity, and alignment with ARXIVE's objectives. Participants contribute to:

- **Experiments:** Testing and validating ARXIVE tools and methodologies in real-life scenarios to generate feedback for refinement.
- **Cultural Heritage Preservation:** Implementing projects that improve documentation, analysis, and sustainable management of cultural heritage assets.
- **Creative Projects:** Developing innovative digital narratives and visualizations that enhance accessibility, engagement, and public understanding of cultural heritage.

Through these activities, FSTP participants act as critical agents for adoption, scaling, and impact assessment. They bridge the project with the broader ECHOES and ECCCH ecosystem, helping to align local initiatives with European-level objectives, standards, and practices. Participants also support capacity building by sharing methodologies, tools, and insights, ensuring the long-term sustainability and replication of ARXIVE outputs across the sector. By funding work that matters, ARXIVE ensures that its outputs are not only tested and validated but also actively contribute to the transformation, innovation, and digital resilience of cultural heritage institutions throughout Europe.

Work Package Leaders: Each work package (WP) will have a designated leader and deputy, in charge of defining and following up on progress and specific objectives, suggesting contingency plans and risk mitigation strategies; coordinating discussions among participating institutions; chairing meetings of work package teams, and providing the agenda and minutes; advising the PMB on technical matters related to the WP; supervising the quality assurance of the deliverables; and supporting the PM in reporting duties. All WPLs report to the PMB.

Table 11: Work Package Leaders

WP Number	WP Title	Lead Beneficiary
WP1	Field work requirements elicitation and local community engagement	VILS - Stevi Theodosiou
WP2	Bibliography annotation design and development	FORTH - Xenophon Zabulis
WP3	CHO authoring tools design and development	FhG - Christoph Lange-Bever
WP4	Integration and deployment with ECCCH and other platforms	OKFNGR - Lazaros Ioannidis
WP5	Use-Case Pilots Implementation and Training Materials	INOVA+ - Nuno Carmeiro
WP6	FSTP, Capacity Building, Workshops, and Digital Innovation Toolkit	LUH - Alexandra Garatzogianni
WP7	Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation, Sustainability	INOVA+ - Inês Francisco
WP8	Project Management and Coordination	LUH - Alexandra Garatzogianni

Ethics and Legal Management

Ethical and legal considerations are central to the ARXIVE project and its research and innovation activities. The ARXIVE partner Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Universität Hannover (LUH) leads WP8, overseeing all tasks related to legal, ethical, and compliance aspects. They provide guidance to ensure that consortium partners appropriately address legal and ethical issues and embed key principles into their research and innovation activities.

T8.3, Gender, Ethical, Legal, Social and Cultural Accountability and Compliance (GELSCAC), led by VILS: This task integrates ethics and compliance at the task level, fulfilling the European Commission’s request for formal ethics oversight. ARXIVE ensures adherence to applicable legal frameworks, including GDPR, the EU AI Act, intellectual property, and national and international legislation related to cultural heritage.

Scope and Responsibilities:

- Ensure that bibliographic and cultural heritage data are accurately attributed, traceable, and legally compliant, including versioning, provenance tracking, and licensing.
- Address legal, social, cultural, and environmental dimensions to maintain the long-term impact, accessibility, and sustainability of ARXIVE tools and methodologies.
- Embed ethics and compliance into quality assurance, risk management, and milestone verification processes.
- Support capacity-building for end-users on legal and ethical topics through trainings, workshops, and webinars.

Stakeholder Engagement: ARXIVE engages a wide range of cultural heritage professionals, including librarians, curators, conservators, archaeologists, historians, data scientists, and AI specialists, to co-create solutions that are practical, interoperable, and legally and ethically sound. Public-facing activities such as exhibitions and pilot events demonstrate compliance and stimulate sustainable uptake of project outputs.

Integration Across Project Pillars:

- **Community Pillar:** Engage end-users early to address adoption and acceptability challenges.
- **Sustainability Pillar:** Ensure outputs remain accessible, interoperable, and compliant with evolving legal and ethical standards.
- **Technology and Innovation Pillars:** Incorporate AI, digital humanities, and cloud-based workflows while safeguarding privacy, rights, and cultural heritage integrity.

Through this framework, ARXIVE ensures that all research, experiments, and supported third-party projects operate in full compliance with ethical and legal standards while promoting transparency, reproducibility, and responsible innovation.

Table 12: Ethics & Legal Responsibilities

Task / Area	Responsible Partners	Key Actions	Compliance & Standards	Stakeholder Involvement
WP8, Legal & Ethical Oversight	LUH, VILS	Oversight of ethical/legal issues, guidance to consortium	GDPR, EU AI Act, IPR, national/international heritage laws	All partners, end-users
T8.3, GELSCAC	LUH, VILS	Gender, ethical, legal, social & cultural accountability; compliance monitoring	Ethics embedded in R&I tasks, bibliographic and CH data traceability, licensing	CH professionals, librarians, curators, archaeologists, AI specialists
Capacity Building & Training	LUH, VILS	Workshops, webinars, focus groups on ethics & legal aspects	FAIR principles, privacy, data ownership, digital heritage standards	End-users from CH sector, pilot partners
Public Engagement / Dissemination	Consortium	Pilot exhibitions, narrative-driven storytelling, showcasing compliant practices	Compliance with dissemination and IP guidelines	CH stakeholders, general public

While T8.3 focuses on continuous monitoring and enforcement of ethics and inclusivity **T1.4**

Ethical and Intersectional research innovation and practice framework -also lead by VILS- is responsible for defining and developing, **D1.2 an Ethical and Intersectional research innovation and practice framework.**

It focuses on research based on stakeholders' insights and international policies and standards, defines the principles of ethics and intersectionality to ensure inclusivity and creates actionable pathways for compliance. Deliverable D1.2 serves a dual purpose: it supports the internal ethical framework of the project, but it is also designed to be a practical guideline for external users in the Cultural Heritage (CH) sector. Apart from core legal and ethical requirements for ARXIVE's innovation the framework will incorporate actionable pathways, tools and resources for applying the ethical and intersectional framework directly within the cultural heritage sector.

3.3 Conflict Resolution Procedures

Although the ARXIVE project has a clearly defined structure with assigned roles and responsibilities, conflicts may occasionally arise. The project follows a structured, incremental procedure to resolve conflicts at the appropriate level, ensuring that issues are addressed promptly, transparently, and amicably.

Procedure Overview

- **Initial Resolution:** Potential conflicts should be reported immediately to the Project Coordinator (PC) by the relevant Work Package Leader (WPL), or directly by any beneficiary. The PC will attempt to resolve the issue through discussion or by calling an ad-hoc meeting or teleconference.
- **Escalation:** If unresolved, the WPL may communicate the issue to the Scientific/Technical Lead (STL), who will coordinate with the PC and organize an extraordinary Project Management Board (PMB) meeting.
- **Monitoring:** All conflicts are documented in a Conflict Monitoring Log, tracking actors involved, reasons, arguments, proposed solutions, and final decisions. The PC ensures oversight of all conflicts and their resolution progress.
- **Voting Mechanism:** For serious conflicts, decisions in the PMB follow the Grant Agreement:

Each beneficiary represented has one vote.

Decisions are taken by majority; in case of a tie, the PC casts the deciding vote.

- **Emergency PMB Session:** For persistent or serious conflicts that may endanger the project, the PC can call an emergency PMB meeting within 21 days. The quorum is two-thirds of votes. The PMB will attempt full consensus; if unresolved, options include involving the EC Project Officer or seeking external advice to implement a final resolution. The consortium is committed to resolving conflicts quickly and amicably, ensuring that disputes do not hinder project progress.
- **Application Across the Project:** This conflict management framework applies to all project activities, including decisions involving the Advisory Board (AB), ELTF, and FSTP participants. All interactions and decision-making follow this unified procedure, ensuring consistency, fairness, and alignment with Horizon Europe requirements.

3.4 Change Request / Amendment Procedures

Change Requests (CRs) are initiated whenever the project's content, scope, or execution requires modification, including but not limited to:

- Changes to the work plan, deliverables, or milestones
- Modifications in partner roles or responsibilities
- Budget reallocations or adjustments to resource use
- Extensions of project duration or significant technical changes

Partners must not submit Change Requests directly to the European Commission (EC). The Project Coordinator (PC) is the sole official contact for submitting requests to the EC.

Procedure:

- **Initiation:** Any partner identifying a need for a change informs the PC, who provides guidance on the proper procedure.
- **Preparation:** Following instructions from the Project Manager, the requesting partner prepares a written Change Request using the internal template and submits it to the Project Manager.
- **Internal Review and Approval:** The Project Manager adds comments and recommendations and refers the Change Request to the General Assembly Meeting (GAM) for discussion and voting. Approval by the GA is required, as changes may affect contractual information.
- **Submission to the EC:** After GA approval, the PC submits the Change Request to the EC for official approval. A change becomes effective only after EC approval.
- **Monitoring and Documentation:** The lifecycle of each CR is recorded in a Change Request Log in a secure, consortium-approved internal repository, capturing:
 - Initiating partner(s) and actors involved
 - Reason for the change
 - Proposed resolution
 - GA decision and EC approval
 - Final implementation and closure

The lifecycle of each Change Request is tracked in a Change Request Log, recording:

- Initiating partner(s) and actors involved
- Reason for the change
- Proposed resolution
- GA decision and EC approval

Communication and Governance:

- All partners are kept informed throughout the CR process to ensure transparency and coordination.
- The CR process is integrated with overall project governance, conflict management, and reporting procedures to maintain alignment across WPs and activities.

- CRs should be submitted as early as possible to allow sufficient time for review and EC approval.

This process ensures transparency, traceability, and compliance with contractual obligations while allowing the consortium to adapt effectively to evolving project needs.

Figure 2: EC Notification

4 Internal Communication

Effective internal communication is essential to ensure that all ARXIVE project components are coordinated, compliant with contractual, legal, ethical, and financial obligations, and deliver on project objectives within the planned schedule and budget. The ARXIVE consortium has established comprehensive procedures to manage communication across all Work Packages (WPs) and project activities, ensuring transparency, traceability, and alignment with Horizon Europe and EOSC requirements.

The Coordinator (LUH) is responsible for overseeing, guiding, and chairing all consortium-wide communication, including plenary meetings, Project Management Board (PMB) teleconferences, and interaction with the European Commission (EC). The Coordinator ensures that all project communications are aligned with internal governance, ethical standards, and legal obligations.

Communication procedures support:

- The proper implementation of management structures.
- Planning, monitoring, and coordination of partner activities.
- Organization of consortium-wide and WP-level meetings.
- Administration support, including tracking deliverables, milestones, and progress reports.
- Liaison with the EC and their reviewers.
- Financial management and reporting.
- Ensuring ethical, legal, and compliance obligations are communicated and upheld.

The following sections describe the tools, roles, principles, and processes underpinning internal communication within ARXIVE.

- A Web-based project-specific information space for communication among the Project members and with the European Commission. Access will be granted on an invitation-only basis for all confidential information, though the general aim of the project is to run its activities openly and transparently. This environment (Google Drive folder or comparable) will include information about the ARXIVE project and associated procedures and templates, minutes of meetings, final decisions taken by the GAM.

- MS Teams will be used to store sensitive data such as the applications for funding, evaluation reports of applicants and participants, payment and contract details, personal data, etc. Reports of the results of the funding from the consortium will also be filed.
- A project-wide email distribution list will be set up for the preparation of the work, where partners exchange information, ideas and opinions. The list may also be used as a bilateral communication tool between partners, keeping the other partners informed of the progress in project tasks.
- Additional mailing lists: Each WP leader is welcome to set up WP specialized mailing lists.

The following sections 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3 describe the different internal communication mechanisms to be used by the project partners within the consortium.

4.1 Roles and Responsibilities

In the ARXIVE project, the following roles and responsibilities are distributed among all project partners:

- **Coordinator (LUH):** Chairs plenary meetings, GA teleconferences, and PMB sessions; oversees the dissemination of agendas and minutes; ensures timely submission of Change Requests, deliverables, and reports to the EC; supervises the secure archiving of documents.
- **Work Package Leaders (WPLs):** Organize WP-level meetings, prepare agendas, coordinate deliverable production, and maintain records of WP discussions and decisions.
- **Task Leaders:** Report progress to WPLs and present task-level updates during teleconferences.
- **Project Manager (PM):** Assists the Coordinator in agenda preparation, monitors progress, ensures adherence to deadlines, and communicates decisions to relevant partners.
- **All Partners:** Contribute to meetings, provide updates on tasks, and comply with communication protocols, including timely sharing of personnel changes or updates impacting the project.

4.2 Communication Tools and Principles

Internal communication relies on **EC-approved virtual platforms, email, and formal documentation**. All communication is guided by the following principles:

- **Transparency:** Decisions, agendas, and minutes are documented and accessible to relevant partners.
- **Traceability:** Records of discussions, decisions, and action items are maintained systematically.
- **Efficiency:** Communication is targeted to relevant recipients to avoid unnecessary duplication.
- **Compliance:** Sensitive information follows GDPR, IPR, and internal confidentiality rules.
- **Integration:** Communication is aligned with conflict resolution, governance, and reporting structures.

Primary channels:

- **Email:** Primary means of communication for formal messages. Mailing lists are established per WP, coordinated by WPLs, and a consortium-wide distribution list is maintained by the Coordinator.
- **Virtual Meetings:** Microsoft Teams is used for teleconferences, task-level meetings, and PMB sessions.
- **Face-to-Face Meetings:** Plenary meetings are scheduled approximately every six months to review project progress, strategic decisions, and major deliverables.

4.3 Meeting Structures

4.3.1 Teleconferences

In our project, we distinguish between the following 4 types of teleconferences:

- **Monthly WP8 Coordination Telcos:** Led by LUH, involving all WPLs and Task Leaders. Focuses on progress reporting, task coordination, and identification of issues.
- **Project Management Board (PMB) Telcos:** Convened as needed to discuss higher-level items, approve decisions, and implement voting processes.
- **Task-level WP Meetings:** Organized by WPLs for ongoing coordination, deliverable preparation, and task management.
- **Urgent Matters:** Addressed promptly via email or other approved communication channels.

4.3.2 Plenary and Face-to-Face Meetings

The ARXIVE Plenary meetings occur approximately every six months and combine consortium-wide discussions with dedicated WP sessions. The dates and locations are agreed during monthly teleconferences; if consensus is not reached, a scheduling poll ensures broad availability. The first-year planned meetings look as follows:

Table 13: Meetings planned in Year 1

Month	Type	Mode	Organizer
M01 2026	Kick-off	Online	LUH
M06 2026	Plenary	TBD	LUH
M12 2026	Plenary	TBD	LUH

The plenary meetings address overall project progress, strategic decisions, and cross-WP coordination.

4.4 Agendas, Minutes, and Documentation

All meetings require a clear agenda including discussion points, venue or teleconference details, and attendees. The plenary, GA, and PMB agendas are distributed by the Coordinator at least 14 days in advance. The minutes are recorded and circulated no later than 14 days after each

meeting. The WP and task-level meetings are documented by WPLs; summaries are shared with the Coordinator. The templates for agendas, minutes, and presentations are maintained in a secure, consortium-approved internal repository.

Table 14: Meeting Timelines

Meeting Type	Notification	Agenda Circulation	Add Agenda Items	Minutes Distribution
Ordinary	45 days	21 days	14 days	14 days
Extraordinary	15 days	10 days	7 days	14 days

4.5 Reporting and Monitoring

The WP Leaders provide monthly updates to the Coordinator on task and deliverable status. The PM monitors overall progress, highlights risks, and ensures alignment with contractual and ethical obligations. The outputs, including FSTP reporting and milestone deliverables, are integrated into regular communication cycles. The version control is maintained for all documents, ensuring historical traceability and accountability.

4.6 Confidentiality, Ethics, and Compliance

Confidentiality, Ethics and Compliance encompass the following:

- All communications with respect GDPR, IPR, and EU ethical standards, including the EU AI Act.
- Sensitive data (personal data, contracts, financial information) is accessible only to authorized partners.
- Ethical and legal updates from WP8 (GELSCAC) are communicated promptly to ensure all partners remain compliant.
- Training and guidance on ethical and legal compliance are provided to WP teams as needed.

4.7 Coordination with the European Commission

The coordination activities with the European commission includes the following:

- All official communications and submissions to the EC are handled by the Coordinator.
- This includes Change Requests, reports, deliverables, and updates on FSTP or other funded activities.
- Partners provide the necessary inputs in a timely manner to allow the Coordinator to maintain compliance with deadlines and reporting requirements.

4.8 Technology Stack and Tool Usage

The ARXIVE project relies on a robust set of technical tools and platforms to support development, collaboration, experimentation, and pilot activities. This section provides an overview of the technology stack, explains its role within the project workflows, and establishes guidelines for project members, particularly technical leads, on usage and documentation.

4.8.1 Purpose and Scope

This subsection ensures that all ARXIVE partners:

- Understand which tools and platforms are used across the project.
- Know how to access, contribute, and collaborate using these tools.
- Apply standardized practices for version control, code management, data handling, and documentation.
- Maintain traceability, reproducibility, and transparency of all technical contributions.

4.8.2 Core Tools and Platforms

Table 15: Core Tools and Platforms

Tool / Platform	Purpose	Users / Roles	Notes / Guidelines
GitLab (internal) GitHub (public, integration with ECHOES)	Source code version control, issue tracking, pull requests, releases	Developers, Tech Leads	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use GitLab for internal processes (development, testing) - Sync releases to GitHub to facilitate integration efforts - Participate in WP4 efforts to maintain deployable assets - Follow repository structure and branching conventions. - Use pull requests for code review. - Tag releases to align with deliverable submissions. - Include links to relevant documentation and tickets.
Collaborative Document Repositories (Google Drive / SharePoint)	Project documentation, templates, meeting notes	All partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintain folder structure per WP. - Use standardized naming conventions. - Link code references where relevant.
ARXIVE Development Environment	Local testing, fieldwork tools, offline-first applications	Developers, Field Technicians	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Follow standard environment setup guides. - Document dependencies and software versions.
ARXIVE Testing Environment	Online infrastructure to host app containers	Developers, Tech Leads	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deploy major releases to be tested by end users
Data Repositories (ECCCH / Zenodo / Local Repositories)	Storage and sharing of datasets, 3D models, annotated bibliographies	All partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure FAIR compliance. - Track data provenance and versioning. - Annotate datasets with metadata.

ML / NLP / Semantic Tools	AI-assisted annotation, semantic enrichment, bibliographic analysis	Developers, WP Leads	- Maintain clear documentation for models and pipelines. - Track updates and evaluation metrics.
Communication Tools (Slack / Teams / Email Lists)	Issue reporting, coordination, notifications	All partners	- Use official channels for task updates. - Avoid sharing sensitive credentials in public channels.

4.8.3 Guidelines for Tech Leads

Tech leads are responsible for maintaining and updating this section as the project evolves. Their responsibilities include:

- 1. Documenting Tool Usage:**
 - Add new tools or platforms as they are adopted.
 - Record versions, configuration, and integration points.
 - Include references to user guides, setup instructions, and training material.
- 2. Maintaining Repository Standards:**
 - Ensure all repositories follow the agreed structure, naming conventions, and access permissions.
 - Track contributions and code reviews.
 - Enforce versioning and tagging rules for deliverables.
- 3. Pilot-Specific Adaptations:**
 - Detail how tools are applied in pilot scenarios, including offline fieldwork setups.
 - Describe any custom scripts, data pipelines, or configurations used in experiments.
 - Record lessons learned and recommended adjustments.
- 4. Collaboration and Access:**
 - Define who has read/write/admin access for each tool.
 - Ensure secure sharing of credentials and compliance with GDPR and internal policies.
- 5. Linking to Deliverables and Reporting:**
 - Reference how tools support deliverable creation and innovation outputs.
 - Ensure traceability between code, data, documentation, and project milestones.

4.8.4 Recommendations for Partners

For the ARXIVE partners, there are several recommended steps to be followed:

- Always consult this section before adopting new tools.
- Follow documented workflows to avoid duplication or inconsistencies.
- Provide feedback on usability, integration issues, or improvements to tech leads.
- Maintain logs of major updates to support internal audits and EC reviews.

5 External Communication

External communication covers all dissemination and outreach activities aimed at promoting ARXIVE’s results, engaging potential adopters, and maximizing the visibility, impact, and uptake of project outputs. This chapter defines the principles, responsibilities, tools, and procedures for all partners when communicating externally, while ensuring compliance with Horizon Europe requirements, confidentiality, intellectual property rights (IPR), ethical standards, and strategic alignment with ECCCH and ECHOES.

5.1 Objectives

External communication in ARXIVE is designed to:

1. **Promote project results** to a wide audience, including cultural heritage (CH) institutions, SMEs, research bodies, policymakers, and the public.
2. **Enhance adoption and uptake** of ARXIVE tools, methodologies, and outputs across Europe.
3. **Align with Horizon Europe rules**, including Open Access, EU funding acknowledgment, and responsible dissemination.
4. **Ensure confidentiality and IPR protection** while enabling transparent and structured communication.
5. **Support strategic collaboration** with ECCCH, ECHOES, and other sister projects to maximize collective impact.
6. **Strengthen sustainability and legacy**, ensuring ARXIVE outputs continue to be used and adapted after project completion.

5.2 Roles and Responsibilities

In the ARXIVE project, the partners could play one or multiple of the following roles:

- **Community Lead (CL, WP7):** Oversees all external communication and dissemination activities; validates content to ensure alignment with the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.1), EU rules, and project confidentiality/IPR obligations.
- **Coordinator (LUH):** Chairs the dissemination process for high-profile and cross-project communications; ensures compliance with Horizon Europe branding, disclaimers, and strategic messaging; supervises engagement with ECCCH and ECHOES.
- **Work Package Leaders (WPLs):** Support dissemination of WP-level results and provide updates on activities to the CL.
- **FSTP Participants and Third Parties:** May engage in communication and dissemination activities, provided their outputs are approved by the CL and aligned with project objectives and EU rules.
- **All Partners:** Ensure that any external communication is pre-approved, accurate, and compliant with EU, ethical, and IPR requirements.

Key Principle: No project outputs or results may be disseminated externally without **prior review and approval by the CL**, and in cases of strategic importance, by the Coordinator.

5.3 Communication Channels and Tools

The Dissemination and Communication Plan (D7.1) defines all approved channels and tools. These include:

- **Project Website:** <https://arxive-eccch.eu/home/> for public dissemination of news, events, and outputs.
- **Social Media Accounts:** Official ARXIVE channels on, LinkedIn, Instagram, Youtube, Zenodo and OpenAire to reach broad audiences.

Table 16: ARXIVE Social Media Accounts

Platform	Link
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/arxive-eccch/
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@ARXIVE_ECCCH
Instagram	@arxive_eccch
Zenodo	@ARXIVE_ECCCH
OpenAire	ARXIVE ECCCH

- **Traditional Materials:** Brochures, flyers, posters, and conference materials approved by the CL.
- **Workshops, Seminars, and Exhibitions:** Organized by partners to showcase ARXIVE outputs and methods.
- **Collaborations:** Joint events, webinars, and publications with ECCCH, ECHOES, and other sister projects.

All communications follow **consistent branding, messaging, and EU visibility rules**, ensuring ARXIVE is clearly identified while highlighting collaboration with ECCCH and ECHOES.

5.4 Horizon Europe Compliance

All external dissemination must adhere to **Horizon Europe rules**:

Funding Acknowledgment:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101233418.”

Disclaimer:

“This [insert type of result] reflects only the author’s views and the European Commission does not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.”

Logo and Emblem Rules:

- The EU emblem must be prominent when displayed with other logos.
- All publications, websites, presentations, and other materials must comply with EU visibility and branding guidelines.
- Partners must verify compliance prior to any publication or dissemination activity.

5.5 Strategic Alignment with ECCCH and ECHOES

ARXIVE’s external communication contributes to the broader ECCCH ecosystem, ensuring outputs are interoperable, visible, and adopted across cultural heritage networks. The results, tools, and methodologies are shared with ECHOES and ECCCH stakeholders, aligning dissemination activities and maximizing cross-project impact. The ARXIVE partners may co-host workshops, webinars, and exhibitions with ECCCH and ECHOES, fostering knowledge transfer, collaboration, and capacity building. This form of communication emphasizes ARXIVE’s role as a sister project, ensuring consistent messaging and recognition of joint objectives in publications and events.

5.6 Dissemination of FSTP and Third-Party Outputs

The FSTP participants are encouraged to disseminate their results to wider CH communities, under guidance from the CL. FSTP beneficiaries must also adhere to EU visibility and disclaimer text on their public outputs. All outputs, including annotated bibliographies and digital narratives, must be approved before external communication to ensure alignment with project objectives and Horizon Europe obligations. Feedback from FSTP dissemination informs project refinement, methodological improvements, and cross-project learning, ensuring ARXIVE’s impact is amplified within the ECCCH/ECHOES ecosystem.

5.7 Approval and Workflow

1. **Preparation:** Partners draft communication material. In case of requests for more complex materials, this must be done over email, at least 2 weeks before the event
2. **Review:** The CL checks content for strategic alignment, Horizon Europe compliance, and IPR/ethical considerations.
3. **Coordinator Approval:** LUH approves high-profile or cross-project communication.
4. **Publication:** Material is disseminated via approved channels.
5. **Monitoring:** Engagement metrics are tracked to assess reach, uptake, and impact.

5.8 Monitoring, Reporting, and Evaluation

The WP7 monitors all dissemination activities, ensuring compliance with Horizon Europe rules, ECCCH/ECHOES alignment, and internal communication protocols. Updates will be provided in the project's Technical Reports, as well as **D7.2. and D7.3 (Communication and Dissemination Report I and II, M16 & M28)**. Periodic monitoring reports will be kept in the ARXIVE Drive.

- Periodic reports include:
 - **Metrics of audience reach** (website, social media, events).
 - **Stakeholder engagement**, including FSTP participants and CH end-users.
 - **Uptake of ARXIVE tools and methodologies** across ECCCH/ECHOES networks.

Lessons learned from dissemination activities are **fed back into the project**, enhancing future communication and cross-project collaboration.

6 Experiments Support & Research

The ARXIVE project adopts a practice-based, action research approach to support experiments, creative projects, and capacity-building initiatives in the cultural heritage (CH) domain. This ensures that the technical, organizational, and societal lessons from engaging with startups, creative teams, and FSTP participants are systematically captured, analyzed, and integrated into project methodologies, tools, and outputs.

6.1 Objectives and Scope

The objectives of ARXIVE experiments and research activities are to:

1. **Support experimentation and innovation** by providing computing, data science, and CH expertise to selected participants, including winners of ARXIVE open calls.
2. **Collect empirical data** on challenges encountered by FSTP participants and other stakeholders in testing bibliographic, digital storytelling, and data management solutions.
3. **Translate lessons learned** into actionable improvements for the ARXIVE toolkit, workflows, and experimental methodologies.
4. **Ensure compliance** with Horizon Europe principles, including ethics, legal requirements, FAIR data, open science, and responsible research & innovation (RRI).
5. **Contribute to European CH infrastructures** through integration with ECCCH and ECHOES, ensuring interoperability, knowledge sharing, and sustainable adoption.

The scope covers all experimental activities across ARXIVE, with WPX leading experimentation coordination and working closely with WPs X and Y to provide support to participants.

6.2 Methodology

ARXIVE follows an action research methodology, combining iterative cycles of observation, reflection, and intervention:

- **Data Collection:** Systematic gathering of technical, methodological, and organizational data from FSTP participants and other experimental projects.
- **Challenge Identification:** Detection of barriers, gaps, and new research questions arising from practical experimentation.
- **Prototyping and Testing:** Collaborative development and validation of workflows, tools, and solutions.
- **Iteration and Refinement:** Continuous improvement of the ARXIVE toolkit and methods based on lessons learned.

All experimental outputs, including software, datasets, and pilot results, are stored in EC-compliant, secure repositories to guarantee traceability, reproducibility, and access.

6.3 Role of FSTP Participants

FSTP participants are core contributors to ARXIVE experimentation:

- They implement projects under WP5 and WP6, testing ARXIVE tools in real-world CH contexts.
- Receive guidance from WPLs and the STL on technical, methodological, and organizational challenges.
- Provide feedback on usability, scalability, and interoperability, which informs the development of the ARXIVE toolkit and future open calls.
- Engage in knowledge sharing with ECCCH and ECHOES, ensuring their outputs contribute to European CH infrastructures.
- Participate in capacity-building activities, including workshops, webinars, and mentorship to strengthen digital skills and tool adoption.
- Their experiments and outputs are carefully documented and evaluated through internal reports and formal deliverables, aligned with GA and Horizon Europe requirements.

6.4 Deliverables

Deliverables from experimental activities follow **strict quality assurance and EC compliance standards**:

1. **Project Report Documents (R):** Formal reports on scientific, technical, or methodological results.
2. **Other (O):** Non-report outputs, such as brochures, flyers, websites, posters, and multimedia.
3. **Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP):** Implements open access in line with Horizon Europe, including a Data Management Plan (DMP, D8.6) and sharing of datasets.
4. **Ethics Deliverables (E):** Outputs related to gender, ethics, legal, social, and cultural accountability (GELSCAC, T8.3), ensuring GDPR, EU AI Act, and other legal compliance.
5. **Dissemination and Communication Outputs (DEC):** Presentations, videos, and public engagement materials.

Deliverables are classified as public or confidential, with confidential outputs restricted to consortium members and EC reviewers.

6.5 Deliverable Preparation and Quality Assurance

To ensure high scientific, technical, and ethical quality, deliverables undergo:

1. **Drafting:** Authors use standard ARXIVE templates and file naming conventions (see Chapter 7).
2. **Internal Review:** Two independent Quality Assurance reviewers provide feedback.
3. **Coordinator Review:** The Coordinator (LUH) ensures compliance with GA requirements, EC guidelines, and deadlines.
4. **Submission:** Deliverables are submitted through the **EC Participant Portal**.

All deliverables incorporate guidance from legal, ethical, and data management tasks, ensuring alignment with GELSCAC (T8.3) and the project's DMP.

6.6 Monitoring and Reporting

The WPLs monitor progress of WP-level experimental activities, reporting risks or deviations to the Coordinator promptly. Regular assessment occurs through monthly WP telcos, plenary meetings, and PMB sessions. Deviations and mitigation measures are documented in management reports, including lessons learned from FSTP experiments. Key performance metrics include adoption of ARXIVE tools, participation in open calls, feedback from participants, and integration with ECCCH/ECHOES platforms.

6.7 Data Management, Ethics, and Legal Compliance

All data, software, and experimental results are stored in **EC-approved repositories**, ensuring FAIR principles. The FSTP participants and partners must adhere to data protection, IP, and licensing rules. Ethical considerations cover participant consent, privacy, inclusivity, and accessibility, ensuring compliance with EU and international frameworks. The GELSCAC framework ensures legal, ethical, gender, social, and cultural accountability is embedded in every experimental and research activity.

6.8 Capacity Building and Training

The ARXIVE project provides the following training and mentorship offers to FSTP participants and consortium members:

- Workshops on AI-powered tools, bibliographic annotation, and digital storytelling.
- Guidance on legal and ethical aspects, including data management and IPR.
- Sessions on ECCCH/ECHOES integration, interoperability, and knowledge-sharing.

This ensures that participants can apply ARXIVE tools effectively, adopt best practices, and contribute to European CH infrastructures.

6.9 Risk Management

The risks for experimental activities are tracked at WP and consortium levels. Key risks include technical challenges, delays, legal or ethical constraints, and data management issues. The Coordinator and STL are responsible for monitoring, mitigation, and escalation to PMB if required. Risk monitoring ensures timely intervention and continuous improvement of tools and methodologies.

6.10 Feedback and Evaluation

A structured **feedback loop** ensures lessons learned are captured, documented, and applied. FSTP and other experiment outputs are reviewed for **quality, compliance, and interoperability**.

Insights from experiments feed directly into:

- ARXIVE toolkit updates.
- Open calls design.
- Capacity-building materials.
- Contributions to ECCCH/ECHOES and broader CH community.

Key Principles:

1. All research and experimental activities follow **action research methodology**, ensuring iterative learning and continuous improvement.
2. **FSTP participants are central**, providing real-world testing and feedback for tools and workflows.
3. Deliverables are **quality-assured, compliant with Horizon Europe rules, and identifiable as ARXIVE outputs**.
4. **Ethics, legal, and data management requirements** are embedded in all activities.
5. Experiments contribute to **ECCCH/ECHOES integration and knowledge transfer**, strengthening the European CH ecosystem.

7 Project Deliverables

This chapter provides a comprehensive description of the structure, management, and quality procedures for all ARXIVE project deliverables produced over the course of the project. Deliverables encompass reports, datasets, software, communication materials, and other outputs, and are subject to rigorous standards for readability, completeness, consistency, ethical compliance, and EC reporting requirements.

7.1 Document and File Naming

All project deliverables must follow a **standardized naming convention** to ensure traceability and clarity.

Format:

- ARXIVE-<WPX>-<D/TYY>-<Date>-<Version>.<ext>
- <WPX>: Work Package identifier (e.g., WP1, WP7). Use WP0 if no WP is applicable.
- <D/TYY>: Deliverable or Task number (e.g., D1.1, T3.2).
- <Date>: Date of the deliverable version in YYYYMMDD format.
- <Version>: Versioning identifier (v1, v1.1, ..., Final).
- <Ext>: File type (docx, pdf, xlsx, pptx, etc.).

For software deliverables, each file must include a standardized header indicating copyright and licensing, e.g., MIT License.

7.2 Reference Documents and Templates

The Reference Documents and Templates encompass the following aspects:

- Deliverable templates (document, Word, PDF, or interactive collaborative versions) will be centrally stored in the project's EC-compliant document repository.
- Each deliverable must be transferred to the final Word template and exported as PDF for EC submission.
- Templates include standardized sections: title, authors/contributors, executive summary, conclusions, references, ethical and legal compliance statement, and metadata.

7.3 Deliverable Types

ARXIVE deliverables fall into several categories:

1. **Project Reports (R)**: Formal documents detailing results, progress, or findings.
2. **Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP)**: Datasets and associated documentation supporting FAIR principles, open access, interoperability, and reuse. Includes **Data Management Plans (DMPs)**.
3. **Other Deliverables**: Brochures, websites, flyers, posters, visualizations, and software outputs.
4. **Ethics & Compliance Deliverables**: Outputs that require special attention to legal, social, gender, cultural, or ethical considerations.
5. **Communication & Dissemination Outputs (DEC)**: Deliverables supporting external communication and engagement.

Deliverables are classified by dissemination level: public (PU) or confidential (CO), with confidential deliverables restricted to consortium members and EC access.

7.4 Internal Review and Quality Assurance

All deliverables undergo a **multi-level internal review** before submission to the European Commission:

- **Quality Criteria:**
 1. **Readability**: Clear language, acronyms explained, proper formatting.

2. **Completeness:** Alignment with proposal objectives, inclusion of required sections, and clear executive summary.
 3. **Consistency:** Coherence across chapters, consistency with other deliverables and WPs, and technical accuracy.
- **Review Roles:**
 1. **Task Leader:** Primary responsibility for deliverable content.
 2. **WP Leader:** Oversees deliverable quality and integration with WP objectives.
 3. **Community Lead:** May review for relevance, engagement, and dissemination aspects.
 4. **STL (Scientific/Technical Lead):** Reviews technical deliverables and ensures compliance with EC standards.
 5. **Coordinator (LUH):** Performs final approval and submission to the EC.
 - **Internal Review Process:**
 1. Deliverable draft submitted to reviewers 4 weeks before the due date.
 2. Reviewers provide feedback within 2 weeks.
 3. The author revises and submits the final version at least 1 week before submission.
 4. Coordinator ensures layout, metadata, ethical statements, and compliance are correct.
 5. Deliverable submitted in PDF format to the EC via the Participant Portal.

The following table provides an overview about the deliverables and their reviewers for the first 12 months:

Table 17: Deliverables Overview and Reviewers for the first twelve months

Del No	Deliverable Title	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Diss Level (PU, CO)	Due date in months	1st Reviewer	2nd Reviewer
D7.1	Communication and Dissemination Plan	INOVA+	R	PU	M3	LUH	OKFNGR
D8.1	Project Management Plan	LUH	R	PU	M3	FORTH	VILS
D8.2	Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan	LUH	R	PU	M6	VILS	FORTH
D8.6	Data Management Plan (DMP) I	LUH	DMP	SEN	M6	NLG	VILS
D5.1	Baseline Assessment of Use Case Pilots	INOVA+	R	PU	M8	MMP	LUH
D2.1	Retro-Digitised and Audiovisual Sources Parsers I	FORTH	OTHER	PU	M9	FhG	OKFNGR
D4.1	Data Alignment Results I	OKFNGR	DATA	PU	M10	FhG	FORTH
D7.4	Cooperation Pathways with Related Projects and Initiatives	INOVA+	R	PU	M10	LUH	OKFNGR
D1.1	Cultural Heritage Methodology and Workflow Baseline for Libraries	FORTH	R	PU	M12	LUH	OKFNGR
D1.2	Ethical and Intersectional Research Innovation and Practice Framework	VILS	R	PU	M12	NLG	OKFNGR

D1.3	Stakeholder Hubs Mapping, Application and Engagement	VILS	R	PU	M12	INOVA+	LUH
D1.4	Cultural Heritage Methodology and Workflow Baseline for Archeological Excavations	FORTH	R	PU	M12	MMP	LUH
D2.3	Multimodal Content Analysis and Classification Framework I	FORTH	OTHER	PU	M12	FhG	LUH
D4.3	API Specification I	OKFNDR	R	PU	M12	EUT	LUH
D7.5	Exploitation and Sustainability	VILS	R	PU	M12	INOVA+	LUH
D8.3	Policy Brief I	FORTH	R	PU	M12	LUH	INOVA+

Table 18: Timeline for submission of deliverables

Action	Due Date
Submission by the author to the reviewers	X - 4 weeks
Review due	X - 2 weeks
Final adjustments (if applicable) by the author due	X - 1 week
Approval and submission by the Coordinator due	X

6 weeks before the actual deadline of the deliverable, i.e. 6 weeks before the definite submission of the deliverable to the EC portal, the Coordinator and/or WPL reminds the deliverable lead to finalize the draft document and send it to the reviewers. This way, we make sure that we closely monitor the status of the deliverables and the timely submission of all deliverables to the portal.

7.5 Ethics, Legal, and Compliance Checks

Each deliverable must integrate **ethics and legal compliance**, including:

- GDPR and data privacy considerations.
- EU AI Act compliance where applicable.
- Intellectual property, copyright, and licensing.
- Gender, social, cultural, and ethical accountability (GELSCAC).
- FAIR principles for datasets and open access where relevant.

The **STL, WP Leaders, and Coordinator** ensure that these aspects are checked at every review stage.

7.6 Open Science and Data Management

Deliverables involving data and software outputs must follow open science principles, ensuring accessibility, reproducibility, and interoperability. The metadata must describe provenance, licensing, and version history. The deliverables linked to the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) must include a DMP reference and clearly indicate reuse conditions.

7.7 Interdependencies and Coordination Across WPs

Some deliverables depend on outputs from other WPs; Task and WP Leaders coordinate to ensure timelines are aligned. Any possible dependencies must be documented in the deliverable planning sheets and reflected in the risk register. A profound communication between WPs ensures timely resolution of delays or conflicts.

7.8 Contingency Planning

If a deliverable is delayed or rejected during review:

- The author informs the WP Leader/STL/Coordinator immediately.
- Contingency actions include reallocation of resources, prioritization of updates, or scheduling additional review sessions.
- Significant delays are reported to the EC Project Officer.
- Serious quality issues are escalated through the Project Management Board.

7.9 Cross-Project and ECCCH Alignment

The Deliverables linked to ARXIVE experiments, FSTP projects, or tools must indicate relevance to ECCCH and ECHOES. The outputs are structured to enable reuse by sister projects, promote interoperability, and contribute to the European cultural heritage ecosystem. The coordination with external stakeholders ensures that deliverables maximize impact and align with Horizon Europe dissemination rules.

7.10 Timeline and Milestones

The Deliverables must be produced according to the DoA schedule, with interim versions prepared for iterative feedback. The backward planning from EC deadlines ensures sufficient time for internal review and compliance checks. For large deliverables, intermediate drafts must follow the same review procedures as the final submission.

7.11 Metadata and Documentation

Each deliverable must include:

- Title, WP and Task identifiers, authors, contributors, and reviewers.
- Confidentiality and dissemination level (PU or CO).
- Due date, submission date, and version history.
- Relevant compliance and ethical statements.

This metadata ensures traceability for internal reporting, EC audits, and knowledge management within the consortium.

7.12 Final Submission

The Coordinator (LUH) is responsible for the submission of all deliverables to the EC. All final deliverable documents are submitted in PDF format, with accompanying metadata and optional source files where applicable. All internal review documentation is maintained for audit, reporting, and continuous improvement.

As per the requirement of the ECCCH and in particular of ECHOES, all public deliverables as well as all publications related to the ARXIVE project must be uploaded on Zenodo, by adding the item to the “ECCCH community”, and made available on the main website of ECHOES: echoes-eccch.eu

In ECHOES, the deliverables are published upon submission, even if they are not yet formally accepted by the EC. Should any revisions be requested by the reviewers, the deliverables will then be updated accordingly. Therefore, the deliverables will not only be displayed on the project website itself, but also on the ECHOES website and the ZENODO page as well.

8 Project Reporting

Project reporting is central to ensuring that ARXIVE progresses according to plan, that resources are efficiently used, and that obligations to the European Commission are met. It provides a structured framework to monitor and document technical, scientific, financial, administrative, and ethical aspects of the project, ensuring transparency, traceability, and accountability. Reporting activities support internal decision-making, risk management, quality assurance, and compliance with Horizon Europe rules, Grant Agreement obligations, and ethical/legal frameworks.

Table 19: Overview of project reports

Report	Content	Responsible	Distribution
Project Management Report (M18, M36)	Overview of Project’s status and WP progress	Lead by PC (LUH) with input from all partners	EC
Financial Reporting (M18, M36)	Financial Statements + Audit Certificate if required	Led by PC with contributions from all partners	EC
	Financial Summary Report. Includes ACTUAL costs and effort of all partners	Led by PC with contributions from all partners	EC
Internal Financial Management Report (M6, M12, M24, M30)	Overview of estimated person months and effort of all partners. This report is internal to the consortium and only for Monitoring and Controlling purposes	Lead by PC (LUH) with input from all partners	Internal (at Consortium level)
Internal Management Report (M12, M24, M30)	Overall progress of the project activity	PC, WPL, all partners	Internal (at Consortium level)

8.1 Internal Project Management Reports

Internal management reports are used to monitor work package progress, task execution, deliverable completion, and resource usage. They support the Project Coordinator and the Project Management Board (PMB) in making informed decisions, identifying deviations, and implementing corrective actions.

- **Frequency:** M12, M24, M30 (internal reporting cycles)
- **Content:**
 - Overall WP and task progress
 - Deliverable status and milestones achieved
 - Deviations, risks, and contingency measures
 - Resource utilization (person-months, effort, and estimated costs)
 - Dissemination, exploitation, and communication updates
 - Ethical, legal, and sustainability compliance considerations
- **Preparation and Review:**
 - WPLs and Task Leaders contribute inputs for their respective areas.
 - Draft consolidated by Project Coordinator.
 - Reviewed by WP Leaders, Scientific/Technical Lead (STL), and Community Lead (CL) as needed before internal circulation.

8.2 Internal Financial Management Reports

Internal financial reporting allows the consortium to track actual costs versus planned budget, ensuring optimal use of EU funding and compliance with the Grant Agreement.

- **Frequency:** Every 6 months (M6, M12, M24, M30 for internal monitoring; M18, M36 for EC reporting)
- **Content:**
 - Partner-specific and WP-level cost and effort tracking
 - Forecasts for the upcoming reporting period
 - Deviations, risks, and recommendations for corrective action
- **Process:** Each partner reports expenditures and effort; the Project Coordinator consolidates into an internal financial report for review and guidance.

8.3 External Project Management and Financial Reporting

External reporting meets contractual obligations to the European Commission and supports project reviews.

- **Roles:**
 - WP Leaders: provide WP narrative + deliverables/milestones status
 - Task Leaders: provide task-level highlights + deviations
 - All partners: effort/cost inputs for financial monitoring
 - PC/Coordinator: consolidate and submit
- **Frequency:** M18 (mid-term), M36 (final)

- **Content:**
 - Technical and scientific progress versus objectives
 - Deliverable and milestone completion status
 - Deviations, risk assessments, and contingency actions
 - Dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities
 - Administrative and financial reporting (actual costs, person-months)
 - Compliance with ethical, legal, and Horizon Europe obligations.
- **Financial Statements:**
 - Submission of Form C by each partner
 - Audit certificates when required by EU thresholds
- **Process:**
 - Consolidation of partner inputs by Project Coordinator
 - Internal review to ensure consistency, accuracy, and GA compliance
 - Submission via EC Participant Portal in the required formats

8.4 Cascading Funding Reporting

ARXIVE implements cascading funding to support startups, creatives, and third parties. Reporting ensures fair, transparent, and auditable allocation of funds.

- **Requirements:**
 - Clearly defined eligible activities and recipient categories
 - Award criteria and maximum grant amounts
 - Documentation of evaluation, selection, and award procedures
- **Principles:**
 - **Excellence:** Funding awarded to high-quality proposals
 - **Transparency:** All decisions clearly documented
 - **Fairness & Impartiality:** Equal treatment for all applicants
 - **Confidentiality:** Protection of proposals and sensitive information
 - **Efficiency:** Rapid evaluation without compromising quality
- **Monitoring:**
 - Tracking of recipients, amounts awarded, and outcomes
 - Inclusion in internal management and EC reports

8.5 Internal Governance of Reporting

In ARXIVE, there are many different forms of internal governance of reporting:

- **Project Coordinator (LUH):** Consolidates and submits all internal and external reports.
- **Work Package Leaders:** Provide technical, scientific, and task-level inputs.
- **Task Leaders:** Support detailed reporting for individual tasks.
- **Scientific/Technical Lead (STL):** Ensures technical and methodological accuracy.
- **Community Lead (CL):** Validates communication and dissemination reporting.
- **Internal Review:** Structured review ensures accuracy, completeness, and compliance with EC rules before submission.

8.6 Integration with Project Management

Reporting is fully embedded within ARXIVE governance:

- Monthly WP8 Project Management telcos track reporting schedules and pending actions.
- Deviations identified feed into the risk register and mitigation plans.
- Lessons learned from reporting cycles inform continuous improvement of processes and quality assurance.
- All reporting outputs support decision-making at the PMB and strategic project planning.

8.7 Alignment with Horizon Europe and Sister Projects

The Reports are fully compliant with Horizon Europe requirements, including open science, FAIR data, ethical/legal compliance, and sustainability. The cascading funding and internal/external reporting align with sister projects under ECCCH and ECHOES, promoting cross-project synergy and best practices. The reports include visibility of cross-WP collaboration, dependencies, and shared outcomes.

8.8 Quality Assurance and Continuous Improvement

The following quality assurance methods will be implemented in ARXIVE in order to achieve continuous improvement:

- **Structured reporting templates and review procedures** guarantee high-quality reporting.
- **Internal checklists and review cycles** ensure consistency, completeness, and readability.
- Reporting serves as a **feedback mechanism**, allowing for early identification of risks, resource gaps, or deviations.
- Reports contribute to **sustainability assessment, capacity-building evaluation, and legacy documentation** for the consortium and the EC.

9 Innovation Management Process

9.1 Overview

The Innovation Management Process in the ARXIVE project provides a structured methodology to guide, monitor, and scale the adoption of innovative tools, methods, and workflows within the cultural heritage (CH) domain. This process ensures that project outputs, including digital tools, platforms, and frameworks, are effectively deployed, continuously improved, and sustainably integrated into the operational environments of Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums (GLAMs) as well as other cultural institutions. The process leverages a combination of capacity-building initiatives, participatory engagement, AI-powered assistance, evaluation frameworks, and knowledge dissemination to maximize the uptake, scalability, and impact of innovation across the ECCCH ecosystem.

9.2 Objectives

The Innovation Management Process serves the following objectives:

1. **Support Effective Adoption of Tools:** Ensure that ARXIVE-developed tools and methodologies are integrated into CH workflows efficiently and effectively.
2. **Promote Sustainable Innovation:** Foster long-term adoption and scaling of innovations within the ECCCH framework.
3. **Facilitate Participatory Engagement:** Actively involve stakeholders, local communities, and professionals in co-creating, testing, and refining innovative solutions.
4. **Monitor and Evaluate Innovation Impact:** Provide continuous feedback and evaluation mechanisms to assess adoption, effectiveness, and scalability.
5. **Enable Knowledge Transfer and Best Practices:** Develop toolkits, training resources, and documentation that capture lessons learned, ensuring replicability across CH institutions.

9.3 Innovation Management Framework

The framework is structured around five interrelated pillars:

9.3.1 FSTP Implementation and Support

The **Fast-Track Support Programme (FSTP)** is the primary mechanism for fostering applied innovation within the project. Its key elements include:

- **Selection of Innovation Projects:** Through open calls, CH professionals and institutions are invited to propose projects that adopt ARXIVE tools.
- **Guided Support:** Dedicated task forces are assigned to monitor each project, providing hands-on guidance and expertise in implementing innovative workflows.
- **Workshops and Flowcharts:** Practical workshops (both virtual and in-person) and detailed workflow charts are used to train participants in efficient, standardized processes.
- **Innovation Reporting:** Progress and results are documented in an FSTP Innovation Report, capturing lessons learned and best practices for further dissemination.

9.3.2 AI-Powered Tutor and Support Systems

To facilitate continuous learning and innovation adoption, ARXIVE integrates AI-assisted support through a **context-aware chatbot tutor**:

- Provides real-time guidance on workflows, tool usage, and troubleshooting.
- Supports personalized learning paths for CH professionals based on their interaction and expertise level.
- Continuously learns from user interactions to improve assistance quality and responsiveness.
- Reduces dependency on direct expert supervision, promoting autonomous, sustainable innovation adoption.

9.3.3 Participatory Engagement and Co-Creation

Innovation is embedded in local and institutional contexts through:

- **Virtual Drop-In Office Hours:** Regular, interactive sessions allow professionals to practice innovative workflows, such as producing reborn articles, under expert guidance.
- **Community Hubs:** Local stakeholder “hubs” facilitate collaborative design, testing, and refinement of ARXIVE tools.
- **Feedback Loops:** Insights from office hours, workshops, and pilots are systematically collected to inform continuous improvement of tools and methodologies.

9.3.4 GLAM Digital Innovation Toolkit

The GLAM Digital Innovation Toolkit is the central repository for knowledge transfer:

- Modular, multilingual, and practical, designed for adoption in diverse institutional contexts.
- Contains templates, workflows, case studies, and lessons learned derived from FSTP projects and pilot implementations.
- Supports institutions in implementing innovative workflows, ensuring compliance with **FAIR principles** and cultural heritage standards such as **CIDOC-CRM**.
- Promotes scalable and repeatable approaches to CH digital innovation.

9.3.5 Evaluation and Impact Assessment

Continuous assessment is embedded to monitor innovation effectiveness:

- **Innovation Metrics:** KPIs include adoption rate, efficiency gains, user satisfaction, and quality of outputs.
- **Stakeholder Feedback:** Structured surveys, interviews, and workshops capture qualitative and quantitative insights.
- **Iterative Refinement:** Feedback informs iterative improvements to tools, workflows, and support mechanisms.
- **Policy and Recommendations:** Insights from evaluations feed into policy recommendations, supporting sustainable adoption and replication across institutions.

9.4 Process Flow

The Innovation Management Process is iterative and cyclical, ensuring continuous improvement:

1. **Identification:** Open calls, pilot sites, and stakeholder hubs identify opportunities for innovation.
2. **Implementation:** FSTP projects deploy tools, supported by AI tutors and hands-on workshops.
3. **Monitoring:** Continuous tracking of KPIs, feedback collection, and engagement analytics.
4. **Evaluation:** Systematic assessment of adoption, efficiency, impact, and lessons learned.

5. **Dissemination:** Insights, toolkits, and best practices are shared via the GLAM Digital Innovation Toolkit and community networks.
Iteration: Findings feed back into workflow refinement, tool improvement, and strategic guidance for new projects.

9.5 Roles and Responsibilities

Table 20: Roles and Responsibilities

Role	Responsibility
FSTP Task Force	Oversee innovation adoption, provide guidance, monitor progress, and report outcomes.
AI Tutor System	Offer context-aware support, guidance, and adaptive learning to CH professionals.
Local Stakeholder Hubs	Co-create, test, and refine workflows and tools in the local context.
GLAM Institutions	Implement ARXIVE tools, provide feedback, and adopt sustainable workflows.
Project Partners	Develop toolkits, organize training, analyze results, and ensure alignment with ECCCH standards.

9.6 Key Deliverables

There are following 4 key deliverables that will be finalized in the process of the ARXIVE project:

1. **FSTP Innovation Report (D6.1):** Documents results of innovation projects, lessons learned, and workflow adoption strategies.
2. **GLAM Digital Innovation Toolkit (D6.4):** Comprehensive toolkit including templates, best practices, workflows, and case studies.
3. **Evaluation Reports (D6.5):** Analyses of innovation adoption, user feedback, and recommendations for improvement and scaling.
4. **AI Tutor Deployment:** Functional chatbot system integrated with ARXIVE tools and workflows.

9.7 Integration with ARXIVE Pillars

The ARXIVE Innovation Management Process is aligned with the project’s five main pillars, which provide the conceptual and operational backbone for innovation activities:

1. Community Pillar

- Ensures active stakeholder engagement and co-creation of tools and methodologies.
- Provides feedback from GLAM professionals and field practitioners during pilot implementations.
- Supports participatory testing of workflows, annotated bibliographies, and CHO documentation.

2. Knowledge Pillar

- Focuses on building interoperable knowledge frameworks, including 3D reconstructions, digital twins, and enhanced ontologies.
- Ensures that innovative tools are compatible with existing ECCCH infrastructure, FAIR principles, and knowledge graph standards.
- Provides the structured data environment for annotation, semantic enrichment, and analytical tasks.

3. Innovation Pillar

- Drives tool development using iterative, spiral methodologies with continuous end-user feedback.
- Incorporates AI-assisted assistants, NLP pipelines, and collaborative platforms to enhance bibliographic, archival, and fieldwork processes.
- Ensures solutions are practical, user-centered, and adaptable to different professional contexts.

4. Sustainability Pillar

- Guarantees long-term adoption of ARXIVE innovations via training, policy alignment, exploitation strategies, and standardization.
- Maintains ethical, legal, and social accountability while fostering interoperability and accessibility.
- Supports integration with broader European infrastructures such as EOSC and Europeana.

5. Transversal Pillar

- Provides governance, quality assurance, and ethical compliance across the innovation management lifecycle.
- Coordinates project management, risk management, and capacity-building activities, ensuring the robustness of innovation adoption and replication.

By mapping the innovation management process to these pillars, the handbook emphasizes that innovation is not only about tool deployment but also about stakeholder engagement, knowledge structuring, technical robustness, sustainability, and governance. This alignment also ensures that all ARXIVE outputs are deployment-ready, interoperable, and scalable across diverse cultural heritage contexts.

9.8 Future Outlook

The Innovation Management Process in ARXIVE demonstrates a structured, iterative approach to developing, testing, and deploying tools for annotated bibliographies, CHO documentation, and fieldwork workflows. By systematically integrating end-user feedback, AI-powered tools, semantic enrichment, and collaborative platforms, the process ensures that innovations are both technically robust and aligned with professional needs.

The process is underpinned by the five ARXIVE pillars: the Community Pillar ensures stakeholder engagement and co-creation; the Knowledge Pillar provides interoperable data frameworks and digital twins; the Innovation Pillar drives iterative, user-centered tool development; the Sustainability Pillar guarantees long-term adoption and alignment with policy and standards; and the Transversal Pillar ensures governance, quality assurance, and ethical compliance.

Together, these pillars create a resilient and inclusive ecosystem that supports the capture, management, and dissemination of cultural heritage data, fostering innovation that is sustainable, scalable, and fully integrated within the broader European cultural heritage infrastructure.

10 Legal Framework

This chapter outlines the legal, ethical, and compliance framework for ARXIVE under **Horizon Europe (HE)**, covering ethics, the Grant Agreement, and the Consortium Agreement.

10.1 Importance of Ethics

All research and innovation activities carried out under **Horizon Europe** must comply with ethical principles, applicable national and Union legislation, and internationally recognized standards. Ensuring ethical compliance improves research quality, integrity, and societal trust.

Key ARXIVE ethics measures include:

- **Ethics Monitoring:** Ethics Checks and Ethics Audits are conducted throughout the project lifecycle according to HE MGA provisions.
- **Data Protection and Privacy:** All personal data collected by ARXIVE are handled in compliance with **GDPR**. The project implements the principles of:
 - **Proportionality:** Only data necessary for project objectives are collected.
 - **Privacy:** Identifiable personal data are protected, and informed consent is obtained when required (Article 6 GDPR).
 - **Anonymized Data:** No consent or GDPR compliance is required for fully anonymized data.
- **Research Integrity:** The ARXIVE consortium commits to avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, and other research misconduct, following the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.
- **Training and Awareness:** Ethics resources and training sessions are provided to all consortium members, including project-specific guidance on ethical challenges in fieldwork, data management, and participatory research activities.

10.2 Grant Agreement

The ARXIVE partners receiving funding under Horizon Europe are responsible for carrying out research and innovation activities described in Annex I – Description of Action of the HE Grant Agreement (HE GA). The Grant Agreement is a legally binding contract between beneficiaries and the European Commission, setting out:

1. **Core Contract**
2. **Annex I:** Description of Action (DoA)
3. **Annex II:** Estimated Budget
4. **Annex IIa:** Additional Budget Information
5. **Annex III:** Accession Forms

6. Annex IV–VI: Financial Statements and Audit Certificates

The HE GA also establishes obligations for reporting, ethics compliance, financial accountability, and intellectual property management.

10.3 Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement (CA) governs relations among ARXIVE beneficiaries. While the HE GA defines obligations towards the European Commission, the CA regulates internal management, including:

- Decision-making and governance structures
- Allocation and management of EU funds
- Access rights, dissemination rules, and intellectual property management
- Internal dispute resolution

The CA is a legally binding document signed by all beneficiaries. It can be updated by unanimous agreement to reflect changes in the consortium, exploitation strategy, or project scope. The Grant Agreement takes precedence over the CA in case of conflict.

11 Financial Organisation

This chapter outlines the financial rules and procedures for the lump sum project ARXIVE under Horizon Europe.

An increasing proportion of calls for proposals in Horizon Europe are being implemented in the form of lump sum funding, which also includes the ARXIVE project. In lump sum projects, costs are reimbursed via flat-rate payments for completed work packages within a project. In other words, the project budget is fully paid out at the end of a reporting period upon completion of a work package.

Calls for proposals offering lump-sum grants are intended to reduce the error rate, simplify project management (for example, by eliminating the need for expense reports and timesheets), and shift the focus from financial management to project content.¹ The special financing method used for lump-sum projects encompasses some particularities to consider which we will list further below.

In lump sum projects, the internal effort monitoring is for consortium steering only. That means that lump sums are defined up front² and eligibility is based on completed work packages and proper implementation of the Tasks and Work Packages as outlined in the Grant Agreement. Accordingly, the estimated costs must be presented in a plausible and convincing manner in the Project proposal, namely in Annex 1. It also follows from this that documentation of the amount of the costs is not required and that the actual costs of the work are irrelevant.

¹ <https://www.zabala.eu/news/lump-sum-in-european-projects/>

² <https://horizoneuropencppportal.eu/lump-sum>

The granting authority will calculate the amount due to the beneficiary on the basis of the reports submitted in previous interim payments (i.e. beneficiary's lump sum contributions for completed and approved work packages).

Lump-sum amounts must be reported in the cost estimate under the relevant budget categories in accordance with Article 6.2 of the Grant Agreement (GA) and in Annex 2, and the work must be carried out in accordance with the application (Annex 1). All required services must be provided within the period specified in Article 4 of the GA (with the exception of costs related to the final report, which may be incurred later; see Article 21 of the GA)³.

Moreover, lump sum contributions for ongoing/not yet completed work packages will have to be included in the periodic report for the next reporting periods when those work packages have been completed. Partial lump sum contributions for work packages that were not completed (e.g. due to technical reasons) may exceptionally be taken into account. This means that it is possible to declare work packages as partially completed so that a partial lump sum share can be paid out⁴. The Coordinator will indicate the degree of completion which will be then assessed by the European Research Executive Agency (REA). If the justification for the partial completion is not accepted, the full work package or contribution of one or more beneficiaries may be reviewed or even rejected.

The amounts due are paid to the Coordinator who must distribute it to the other beneficiaries without delay. The final payment is equal to the sum of remaining funds up to maximum grant amount and the amount to be paid in the Mutual Insurance Mechanism (MIM, also known as Guarantee Fund). If the difference is positive, it will be paid to the coordinator and if negative, it will be recovered.

The interim payment ceiling is 90% of the maximum grant amount which is the prefinancing plus interim payment.

If the granting authority does not receive the report within the deadline, only lump sum contributions which are included in an approved periodic report will be taken into account (no contributions if no periodic report was ever approved).

One of the biggest advantages of the lump sum payment system is that it is not dependent on successful outcomes and follows a standard payment schedule. Lump sum projects enjoy the same degree of flexibility, and their performance is judged by the same standards⁵.

The above-mentioned information have been checked against the “Lump sum funding in Horizon Europe” section of the website of the European Commission here: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/programmes/horizon/lump-sum/guidance>

³ In German: <https://www.horizont-europa.de/de/Pauschale-Finanzhilfebeträge-Lump-Sum-Grants-3328.html>

⁴ <https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/lump-sum>

⁵ <https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/lump-sum>

12 Conclusion

This document has established the core principles, guidelines, and procedures for the effective management of the ARXIVE project. It outlines the overall governance and decision-making structures, providing a clear framework for both the Project Manager and consortium partners. The handbook defines roles, responsibilities, and reporting obligations, as well as internal and external communication mechanisms, ensuring smooth interaction within the consortium and with stakeholders, including the Advisory Board.

Additionally, the handbook addresses the management of project deliverables, their dissemination levels, and the use of standardized templates for reporting and formal communication, supported by a structured internal review process to ensure quality and compliance. The legal framework emphasizes the importance of ethics, research integrity, and GDPR-compliant data management, while highlighting the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement as binding instruments for the consortium.

Finally, the handbook provides financial management guidance, including cost eligibility, reporting procedures, and categorization of expenses, aligned with Horizon Europe rules. Together, these sections offer a comprehensive reference for managing ARXIVE efficiently, ensuring transparency, accountability, and the successful achievement of project objectives throughout its lifecycle.

13 References

- [1] European Commission (2026), *"Lump sum funding in Horizon Europe"*
- [2] Horizon Europe NCP Portal (2026), *"Lump sum funding"*
- [3] ZABALA Innovation (2026): *"What is lump sum funding in European projects and how does it work?"*
- [4] ECHOES (2026): *"COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES for the ECCCH funded projects"*
- [5] European Commission (2026): *"Horizon Europe Cluster 2 Coordinators' Day – Guidance on Horizon Europe Project Implementation"*
- [6] European Commission (2026): *"Horizon Europe – THE EU RESEARCH & INNOVATION PROGRAMME 2021-2027"*, Date: 22.01.2026

Consortium

